

A Comparative Study of Awareness about NEP-2020 among Government and Private Secondary School Teachers

Nawajish Ali¹ and Nikhat Yasmin Shafeeq^{2*}

¹Research Scholar, Department of Education, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202001

E-mail: gm4461@myamu.ac.in

²Professor, Section of Education, Women's College, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202001

*E-mail: nikhatshafeeq@rediffmail.com

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Keywords:

*Awareness, NEP-2020,
Secondary School and
Teachers*

ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy-2020 was put forward by the “Ministry of Human Resource and Development” (currently known as “Ministry of Education”) on 29th July 2020. The NEP-2020, is a significant reform in country’s educational landscape, aims to overhaul the education system by introducing progressive changes. The present study compared the awareness level of secondary school teachers regarding NEP-2020. The sample consisted of 200 teachers including 108 from government schools and 92 from private schools, out of which 92 were male and 108 were female teachers. A self-constructed tool, comprised of 35 items under four dimensions, was used to collect the data and to assess the awareness about NEP-2020. Data was analysed by using the SPSS software and the statistical techniques used were percentage analysis, t-test, mean and SD. It was found that generally the secondary school teachers were well aware about the NEP-2020. When private and government secondary school teachers were compared, it was found that teachers of government secondary schools have a higher level of awareness in comparison to the private schools. When secondary school teachers were compared on the basis of gender, it was found that female secondary school teachers were more aware in comparison to their male counterparts.

Introduction:

Education is crucial for an individual's success. It has the potential to guide an individual's life positively. Education is a continuous process of knowledge acquisition and the cultivation of inherent human abilities. Education enhances life and fosters tranquilly. It alters the personality of persons and instils confidence in them. It is one of the most fundamental aspects that distinguish humans from all other organisms. Education fosters knowledge, cultivates enjoyment, and serves as the foundation of a civilised community. It is accurate to assert that education serves as a benchmark for the development of numerous nations. In India, education is a fundamental right for every citizen without any discrimination based on age, region, religion, caste, class, creed, gender etc. An educated individual is universally appreciated and treated favourably in the society. Education fortifies democracy by equipping citizens with the necessary tools to engage in the governance process. It serves as a unifying factor to promote social cohesion and national identity. The educational system of any nation reflects the government's priority towards education (Malik and Shafeeq, 2019; Verma and Kumar, 2021).

India is gradually working on its educational policies since independence. Progressive changes in different educational policies can be seen. First policy on education was introduced in 1968, then after 18 years second education policy was declared in 1986 which was revised in 1992. After 34 years third policy on education was introduced in 2020.

The Union Cabinet of India approved the new "National Education Policy-2020" on Wednesday, July 29, 2020. In June 2017, the "Ministry of Human Resource Development"(MHRD) established a committee led by Dr. K. Kasturirangan. The report by this committee was presented on May 31, 2019. This new Policy is based upon the report and recommendations given by Kasturirangan's Committee. This policy is the first initiative of the twenty-first century in the field of education, designed to address the developmental needs of our nation. To build a new system that is in line with the aspirational aims of education in the twenty-first century, national education policy suggests revising and overhauling every element of the educational system, including its governance and regulation. It focuses on "Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education: Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all)", while building upon value systems and traditions of India (Malik and Shafeeq, 2018; Mustafa and Shafeeq, 2019). National Education Policy-2020 highlights its vision as:

"National Education Policy-2020 envisions an education system rooted in Indian ethos that contributes directly to transforming India, that is Bharat, sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society, by providing high-quality education to all, and thereby making India a global knowledge

superpower. The Policy envisages that the curriculum and pedagogy of our institutions must develop among the students a deep sense of respect towards the Fundamental Duties and Constitutional values, bonding with one's country, and a conscious awareness of one's roles and responsibilities in a changing world. The vision of the Policy is to instill among the learners a deep-rooted pride in being Indian, not only in thought, but also in spirit, intellect, and deeds, as well as to develop knowledge, skills, values, and dispositions that support responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living, and global well-being, thereby reflecting a truly global citizen”.

This NEP takes inspiration from both enlightenment principles and a sense of nostalgia, aiming to connect India's rich cultural heritage with a broader global knowledge framework (Ritu Sharma, 2024). This policy focuses on unlocking the creative potential of every individual and believes that education should go beyond just enhancing cognitive skills. The National Education Policy-2020 focuses on enhancing infrastructure and establishing innovative education centres to reintegrate dropouts into mainstream education. It emphasizes monitoring students and their learning progress, offering various pathways for learning that include both formal and informal education options, and involves the support of counsellors or well-trained professionals (Shobha, 2022). It also emphasizes the importance of foundational skills like literacy and numeracy, while also fostering higher-level thinking skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving, along with social, ethical, and emotional development. Additionally, NEP-2020 calls for improvements in the curriculum and teaching methods in schools and colleges. The NEP offers a valuable chance to shift Indian education from a focus on sorting and selection to one centred on human development. This change aims to help every student reach their full potential (Shobha, 2022). It aims to instill a strong respect for fundamental duties and constitutional values, encouraging a sense of belonging to one's country and an understanding of personal responsibilities in a rapidly changing world (Ritu Sharma, 2024). For the NEP to be effectively implemented, it will require increased support; academic, logistical, and financial from everyone involved to truly transform the education system (Yenugu, 2022).

Rationale of the Study:

In this age of globalization, the changing and challenging needs of the society can be tackled only by the well-educated and trained persons, and for the same, quality education is necessary, which can be possible only when a good education policy show a path to achieve this goal. To fulfil these goals and to compete with global education, Indian government introduced this new education policy. To implement any policy or plan it is necessary for different stakeholders to be aware about the same. In this case teachers, especially secondary school teachers who prepare and groom the foundational stones

i.e.,students for the better future of any nation, are one of the most important stakeholders for the better implementation of this policy. So,this studyaimed to assess the awareness levels of secondary schoolteachers towards NEP 2020and compared the awareness levelsof teachers from government and private secondary schools.

Research Questions:

In this study, researchers tried to provide empirical answers to the following research questions:

1. To what extent secondary school teachers are aware about NEP-2020?
2. Isthere exist any significant difference between the awareness level of government and private secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020?
3. Isthere exist any significant differencebetween the awareness levelof female and male secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020?

Objectives of the Study:

In correspondence to the research questions, the objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To study the level of awareness of secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.
2. To compare the awareness level of government and private secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.
3. To compare the awareness level of female and male secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

Hypotheses:

The hypotheses of the above-mentioned objectives are as follows:

H₀₁There is no significant difference between the awareness level of government and private secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

H₀₂There is no significant difference between the awareness level of female and male secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

Population: The population of this study includes all teachers ofsecondary schoolsin the Delhi-NCR region and Aligarh district.

Sample: The sample was selected through random sampling technique andconsists of 200 teachers of secondary schools comprising 108 teachers from government and 92 from private secondary schools and 92 male and 108 female secondary school teachers.

Tool used: The researchers themselves constructed a NEP-2020 Awareness Scale for collection of data (which comprised 35 items corresponding to the four dimensions of NEP-2020 viz. General, School Education, Teacher Education, Making it Happen).

Data Analysis: In accordance with the nature and objectives of the study, the quantitative data was analysed by using SPSS software and statistical techniques used were percentage analysis, mean, standard deviation, and t-test.

Objective Wise Analysis:

Objective No. 1

To study the level of awareness of secondary school teachers towards National Education Policy, 2020.

Table 1: Percentage analysis of awareness level of SSTs about NEP 2020

Level of Awareness	Range of Scores	Frequency	Percentage
Low	79 & below	28	14%
Average	80 – 98	152	76%
High	99 & above	20	10%

Interpretation:

Table-1 indicates that out of the total sample of 200 secondary school teachers, 10% teachers have high level of awareness towards NEP-2020, 76% of secondary school teachers have an average level of awareness towards NEP-2020 and 14% of secondary school teachers have low level of awareness towards NEP-2020.

The result of the percentage analysis may be clearer by the following Pie chart:

Figure-1 Pie Chart showing Awareness Level of SSTs

Objective No. 2

To compare the awareness level of government and private secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

Hypothesis (H₀1)

There is no significant difference between the awareness level of government and private secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

The result was analysed by using independent sample t-test.

Table 2: Comparison between the mean scores of awareness about NEP-2020 among Government and Private SSTs

Type of School	N	Mean	S.D.	Mean Difference	df	t-value	S.E. Difference	Result
Government	108	90.379	7.6178	3.933	198	3.157	1.2461	Significant
Private	92	86.445	9.9806					

Interpretation:

It is evident from Table-2 that the calculated t-value i.e., ‘3.157’ is higher than the tabulated t-value i.e., ‘1.97’ and ‘2.60’ respectively for df 198 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, it is significant at both the level of significance i.e., 5% and 1%. Hence, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the awareness level of government and private secondary school teachers towards National Education Policy, 2020. As the data shows that the mean value of government secondary school teachers (90.3796) is much greater than the mean value of private secondary school teachers (86.4457). Therefore, it may be said that government secondary school teachers are more aware about the NEP-2020 in comparison to the private secondary school teachers.

The result may be graphically presented as given below:

Figure-2: Showing mean scores of awareness about NEP2020 of Government and Private SSTs

Objective No. 3

To compare the awareness level of female and male secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

Hypothesis (H₀2)

There is no significant difference between the awareness level of female and male secondary school teachers towards NEP-2020.

Table 3: Showing mean scores of awareness about NEP-2020 of Male and Female SSTs

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	Mean Difference	df	t-value	S.E. Difference	Result
Male	92	86.0543	10.21351	4.65862	198	3.777	1.23342	Significant
Female	108	90.7130	7.15130					

Interpretation:

It is evident from Table-3 that the calculated t-value i.e., ‘3.777’ is higher than the tabulated t-value i.e., ‘1.97’ and ‘2.60’ for df 198 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance respectively. Therefore, it is significant at both the level of significance i.e., 5% and 1%. Hence, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the awareness level of Male and Female secondary school teachers towards National Education Policy, 2020. As data shows that the mean value of female secondary school teachers (90.7130) is much greater than the mean value of male secondary school teachers

(86.0543), so it may be concluded that female teachers at secondary schools are more aware about NEP-2020 than their male counterparts.

The result may be graphically presented as given below:

Figure 3: Showing mean awareness scores of Male and FemaleSSTs

Findings of the Study:

The findings of the study are as follows:

1. Teachers at secondary schools were found to be widely aware about the National Education Policy-2020. It was found that just 14% of secondary school teachers had a low degree of awareness regarding the National Education Policy-2020, 10% have high level of awareness and 76% have moderate level of awareness.
2. A significant difference was observed in the awareness levels of government and private secondary school teachers regarding the National Education Policy-2020. Government secondary school teachers demonstrated higher level of awareness of the NEP2020 as compared to their counterparts in private schools.
3. Female and male secondary school teachers differs significantly when compared on their level of awareness towards National Education Policy, 2020. Female secondary school teachers were found to be more aware in comparison to their male counterparts.

Conclusions:

Indian Government formulated “National Education Policy-2020” after an exceedingly long span of thirty-four years to fulfil the requirements of society and education system, to raise educational standards globally and enhance the quality of education. Successful implementation of this policy cannot be achieved, unless different stakeholders viz. educational planners, administrators, parents, students and especially teachers have the awareness about this NEP-2020 because teacher’s role is more crucial in every educational program. If the teacher is unaware of the National Education Policy-2020, the provisions may not reach to the target populations. An aware teacher can encourage parents to send their children to schools, to receive required education and be the part of national development as well as encourage students directly to achieve excellence in different fields and contribute to global education. Therefore, it might be argued that the goal of NEP-2020 would not be fulfilled if teachers are not aware about this policy, and it will be extremely challenging to follow the instructions covered in NEP-2020. The findings highlighted the effectiveness of initiatives aimed at promoting awareness of the NEP 2020, as many teachers exhibit moderate to high levels of awareness about the policy. However, the presence of disparities based on institutional type and gender suggests areas where targeted interventions may be needed.

Acknowledgement:

Authors are thankful to the Chairperson, Department of Education, AMU, Aligarh and all the secondary school teachers comprised the sample for providing the data.

References:

- Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2020). Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards achieving its objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 5(2), 19-41.
- Ali, N. (2022). A comparative study of awareness about NEP-2020 among government and private secondary school teachers (Unpublished master's dissertation). Aligarh Muslim University.
- Draft National Education Policy 2019, (<https://innovate.mygov.in/wpcontent/uploads/2019/06/mygov15596510111.pdf>)
- Govinda, Rangachar. (2020). Symposium-New Education Policy NEP 2020: A Critical Examination. *Social Change*. 50. 603-607. 10.1177/0049085720958804.

- Verma, H., & Kumar, A. (2021). New Education Policy 2020 of India: A theoretical analysis. *International Journal of Business and Management Research*, 9(3), 302-306.
- Kalyani, P. (2020). An empirical study on NEP 2020 [National Education Policy] with special reference to the future of Indian education system and its effects on the Stakeholders. *Journal of Management Engineering and Information Technology*, 7(5), 1-17.
- Malik, M., & Shafeeq, N.Y. (2018). Attitude of undergraduate students towards sustainable development. *International Research Journal of Human Resources and Social Sciences*, 5(3), 119-132.
- Malik, M., & Shafeeq, N.Y. (2019). Study of professional attitude of teacher trainees of Government and Private teacher education institutions. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 6(5), 12-18.
- Mustafa, A., & Shafeeq, N.Y. (2019). Value education and role of Teachers in contemporary era. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, IT and Social Sciences*, 9(5), 227-230.
- National Education Policy 2020. https://www.mhrd.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/nep/NEP_Final_English.pdf
- National Policy on Education, 1968: *Government of India* https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/document-reports/NPE-1968.pdf
- National Policy on Education-1986, New Delhi: *Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India*. https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/nep/Policy_1986_eng.pdf
- National Policy on Education-1986, Plan of Action 1992, New Delhi: *Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India*. https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/upload_document/npe.pdf
- Panditrao, M. M., & Panditrao, M. M. (2020). National Education Policy 2020: What is in it for a student, a parent, a teacher, or us, as a Higher Education Institution/University? *Adesh University Journal of Medical Sciences & Research*, 2(2), 70-79.
- Sharma, R. (2024). Qualitative assessment of new policy framework on school education in India. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(4), 391–395.
- Shobha, M. (2022). A study on awareness of NEP-2020 among secondary school teachers. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 4(6), 2582-2160.

- Yenugu, S. (2022). The new National Education Policy (NEP) of India: Will it be a paradigm shift in Indian higher education? *Perspectives: Policy and Practice in Higher Education*, 26(4), 121–129.